

Design of GSM Controlled Electrical Loads

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ABSTRACT

This GSM controlled electrical loads is designed using the Dual Tone Multi Frequency (DTMF) feature. The system is powered by 5volts dc power supply. The system has three electrical loads in which any load could be up to 2.2KVA. The heart of the system is the DTMF chip that converts keypad tones from a phone into binary. The circuit has two electrical wires; the first is connected to the load supply while the other is connected to a mobile phone within the circuit. A resident phone from any location connects to the mobile phone in order to control the loads, using its keypads to switch on and off the loads. Relays via transistors are connected to its output terminals and they will turn on and off the electrical loads depending on the number that is pressed on the resident phone. When a digital 1 is received by the transistor, it will get saturated, short-circuit the collector and emitter thereby switching on the relay.

Keyword: *Dual tone multi frequency (DTMF), GSM controlled loads, Mobile phone, Relay.*

INTRODUCTION

Since the advent of the global system for Mobile Communication (GSM) Device, its usefulness and relevance has continued to blossom in the society. The sophistication of the phone has also evolved in such a way that video and other multimedia data can now be transferred wirelessly. This paper is based on the design of one of such devices that utilizes the GSM network's communication channel for its operation and control.

Electrical loads are mostly controlled with mechanical switches. This switches will determine the state of the load, either it turns off or on. In this paper, the signals from a GSM phone are used to control electromagnetic switches which will in turn be used to control the electrical loads.

Various load control technology such as the power line carrier, telephone modem, WIFI, infrared based technology, frequency modulation (FM), amplitude modulation (AM), Bluetooth and ZigBee were established to facilitate comfort for humans [11].

While the infra-red is reputed to be cheap and easy to assemble, it in itself has some limitations. The major limitation of the infrared is that it has to be line of sight operated.

Another method used in the remote control of electrical appliances is the Radio Frequency (RF) technology. RF eliminates the line of sight problem of the infrared and is mostly used in many remote control installations. However, RF is limited by range as it is only effective within just a few meters.

Hence, the desire to control an electrical appliance using remote, where the appliance can be as far away as possible, while still making the whole system reliable, cheap and robust and using an everyday utilized electronic, is desired. This circuit is able to control multiple loads from any location in the world and its compatibility is assured. In this paper, we will be concentrating on the use of the GSM wireless network to control the electrical loads.

Dual tone multiple frequency DTMF is a feature utilized by keypads to generate sounds when a key on the keypad is pressed.

It is a method of Multi Frequency Shift Keying data transmission [10]. Each button on the keypad represents alphanumeric digits or characters and each of them outputs a unique sound as they are depressed corresponding to specific frequencies or combination of frequencies hence the term "multiple frequency". For example, the sound you hear when you punch "2" on your keypad, is a combination of two unique frequencies (600Hz and 1400Hz). This frequency is so unique that it has been standardized. This means that irrespective of the use of the keypad, either in a GSM phone, a microwave timer machine or in an ATM machine, the sound output when the button '2' is pressed, is always a combination of 600 and 1400 hertz.

In this project, the dual tone multiple frequencies (DTMF) feature will be utilized extensively as the major control of the devices using the GSM is based on it. In the world today, innovation in technology is integral in everyday life. Similar projects have been done to control electrical load in the past through the use of radio frequency, power line carrier, telephone modem, internet, WIFI and Bluetooth. In 2013, V. Bhatia and P. Whig [10] presented the modeling and simulation of electrical load control system using RF technology. Moreover, V. Bhatia and P. Whig [11] designed and simulated the smart elevator control system with Security based on Dual Tone Multi Frequency while in 2014, Sarinee Ouitrakul and Sirichai Watanasophon [12] presented Wireless Load Control Device (WLCD) using GSM module. In June 2012, Abah O. Sunday et al [13] presented a paper on Remote Control of Electrical appliances using GSM Network. Makwana R. et al [14] in the year 2013 presented a Wireless Based Load Control and Power Monitoring System. Finally in 2005, Alkar A.Z et al [14] presented an Internet Based Wireless Home Automation System for Multifunctional Devices in which the system was designed to be low cost and flexible with the increasing variety of devices to be controlled.

3. The Design

In this session, the design calculations on the GSM controlled electrical load circuit is discussed, all the mathematical formulae and technical theories that led to the determination and choosing of the components, their rating and operations were also presented. The block diagram, sub circuits diagram and the full diagram of the complete project is also shown.

The block diagram of the GSM control for electrical load is shown in fig.1:

Fig.1: Block Diagram of GSM Controlled Electrical Loads.

As can be seen from the block diagram, the power supply unit supplies power to the whole system, the GSM decoder circuit is the main input signal unit that accepts the GSM signals. When these signals come, according to the value of the input signals, they will be transmitted to the switching circuit that will now send the value of these transmitted signals to the load control, circuit which will in turn control the loads using the load terminals.

3.1. The Power Supply Unit

Fig.2: Power Supply Unit

The Power supply unit is a circuit comprising of diodes, capacitor, voltage regulator and power indicator. This supplies two DC voltage level to the whole circuit from an AC source, the circuit diagram is as shown above.

3.1.1. Transformer (TR1)

This is the step down transformer. A transformer voltage of 12Vac is required. The current is enough to supply the requirement for the circuit.

The transformer (T1) chosen is 12Vac@300mA.

3.1.2. Rectifier Circuit (D1-D4)

These are the rectifier circuit. The diodes chosen have a peak inverse voltage (PIV) that is able to withstand twice the peak voltage (V_p) of the transformers output and a forward current (D_c) of 1.5 times the output current of the transformer.

$$V_p = \sqrt{2} V_{rms} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Where V_p is the peak voltage of the transformer output.

V_{rms} is the actual output voltage from the transformer = 12Vac

$$V_p = \sqrt{2} \times 12$$

$$V_p = 1.414 \times 12$$

$$V_p = 16.97 \text{Vac}$$

$$D_{(piv)} = 2 \times V_p \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Where $D_{(piv)}$ is the PIV of the rectifier diode

$$\text{Therefore, } D_{(piv)} = 2 \times 16.97$$

$$D_{(piv)} = 33.94.$$

$$\text{And } D_c = 1.5 \times 300 \times 10^{-3}$$

$$D_c = 0.45 \text{A}$$

Therefore the required diode is:

$$PIV \geq 33.94 \text{V}$$

$$D_c \geq 0.45 \text{A}$$

From diode catalogue, the IN4007 has the following characteristics:

$$PIV = 50 \text{V}$$

$$D_c = 1 \text{A}$$

Consequently, the diode chosen is the IN4007

$$D_1-D_4 = \text{IN4007}$$

C₁: This is the filters capacitor. Electrolytic capacitors come with a capacitance and a voltage rating.

3.1.3. Filtering Circuit

The voltage of the capacitor (V_c) must be able to withstand 150% of the output voltage from the diode.

$$V_c = 150\% \text{ of } V_{DP} \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Where V_{DP} is the peak output voltage from the diodes

But V_{DP} is given as

$$V_{DP} = V_p - V_D \dots\dots\dots 4$$

Where V_p is the peak voltage of the transformer

V_D is the voltage drop of the diodes (0.7×2)

$$V_{DP} = 16.97 - 1.4$$

$$V_{DP} = 15.57 \text{V}$$

$$\therefore V_c = 1.5 \times V_{DP} \dots\dots\dots 5$$

V_c is the voltage rating of the capacitor

$$V_c = 1.5 \times 15.57$$

$$V_c = 23.6 \text{V}$$

The capacitance of the capacitor must be such that it could reduce the ripple voltage (V_R) to about 30% of the output peak voltage from the diodes.

$$V_R = 30\% \text{ of } V_{DP} \dots\dots\dots 6$$

From eqn 3, V_{DP} is given as 15.57

$$\therefore V_R = \frac{30}{100} \times 15.57$$

$$V_R = 4.67V$$

From the ripple voltage equation, we could get the capacitance

$$V_R = \frac{I_{max}}{2 \times f \times C_1} \dots\dots\dots 7$$

Where V_R is the ripple voltage

I_{max} is the maximum current from the diodes/ transformers (300mA)

f is the frequency of supply (50Hz)

C is the capacitance of the capacitor in Farads.

$$V_R = 4.67V$$

$$\therefore V_R (2FC) = I_{max}$$

$$C_1 = \frac{I_{max}}{V_R \times 2 \times f} \dots\dots\dots 8$$

Substituting,

$$C_1 = \frac{300 \times 10^{-3}}{4.67 \times 2 \times 50}$$

$$C_1 = \frac{0.3}{467}$$

$$C_1 = 6.42 \times 10^{-4} \text{ F}$$

Converting to μF

$$C_1 = \frac{6.42 \times 10^{-4}}{10^{-6}}$$

$$C_1 = 642.4 \mu\text{F}$$

$$= 642.4 \mu\text{F}$$

This value cannot be obtained in the market and due to the high ripple rejection factor of the voltage regulator, a lower capacitance is chosen. Therefore the capacitance chosen is:

$$C_1 = 470 \mu\text{F} @ 35V$$

U1: This is the voltage regulator.

Regulator specifications:

- Maximum input voltage = 30V
- Maximum output voltage = 5.5V
- Operating temperature = 0%- 150%

For effective Voltage regulation, the minimum input voltage is:

$$V_{min} = V_{out} + V_{ref} \dots\dots\dots 9$$

V_{min} – Minimum input voltage

V_{out} – required output voltage: 5V

V_{ref} – Datasheet Stipulated reference voltage; 3V

$$V_{min} = 5 + 3$$

$$V_{min} = 8V$$

The output voltage after the capacitor is 15.57 volts. This is enough to supply the minimum input voltage (8 volts), therefore, the voltage regulator is comfortably used. The regulator chosen is

$$U_1 = 7805$$

C_2 is a transient capacitor. The rating is stipulated in the 7805 voltage regulator's data sheet as 0.1 μF

Hence,

$$C_2 = 0.1 \mu\text{F}$$

This capacitor helps for smoothening of the output from the voltage regulator. It is also to prevent spikes in the DC output voltage waveform in the event of transient disturbances. It is known as a buffer capacitor whose value is gotten from the data sheet of the regulator.

Current limiting resistor calculation:

$$R_1 = (V_s - V_d) / I_d \dots\dots\dots 10$$

$$R_1 = (5-2) / 10 \times 10^{-3}$$

$$R_1 = 300 \Omega$$

This value of resistor is not in the available, so the appropriate value to use is:

$$R_1 = 330 \Omega$$

Light emitting diode characteristics:

Forward current of..... $10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ A}$ to $10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ A}$

Voltage drop of..... 2V

3.2 The GSM Decoder Circuit

This is the circuit that takes the signal from the connected GSM phone, decodes it and converts it into readable format for the other integrated circuit to utilize. The circuit diagram is as shown in fig.3.

Fig.3: The GSM Decoder Circuit

The heart of the circuit is based on the integrated circuit, MT8870. The datasheet of this integrated circuit stipulates the exact way it is biased. To this effect, the external components used for this block is lifted off directly from the datasheet circuit diagram

3.3 The Switching Circuit

This is the circuit that switches on and off the electrical loads connected to the circuit. The circuit diagram is as shown in fig. 4.

Fig.4: The Switching Circuit

RL₃ : is a switching relay. The parameters of the relays are given as:

- ✓ DC volts: 6V
- ✓ Contact AC current 10A
- ✓ DC Coil resistance: 400Ω

@ An ac voltage of 220volts, the contact of the relay has a power of:

$$P = IV$$

$$P = 10 \times 220$$

$$P = 2.2KW$$

Any electrical device rated within this power works with the circuit

R₇ this is the base resistor for the transistor.

For effective switching, the collector current is about 10 times the base current.

$$I_C = 10 \times I_B$$

Consequently, the resistors relationship is

$$\therefore R_B = 10 \times R_C$$

The resistance of the relay is given as 400Ω

Thus

$$R_C = 400\Omega$$

From the transistor switch equation,

$$R_B = 10R_C$$

$$R_B = 10\Omega \times 4000\Omega$$

$$R_B = 4000\Omega$$

4.7kΩ is chosen for R₇

FIG.5: The Complete Circuit Diagram

3.4. Mode of Operation

The GSM based control for electrical loads is powered by a 5volts dc power supply gotten from a 220 volts ac supply. This power is stepped down by a transformer, rectified by rectifier diodes, filtered by a filter capacitor and regulated by a voltage regulator to produce the required 5 volt d.c supply.

The heart of the circuit is the dual tone multi frequency. This integrated circuit utilizes the keypad tones (DTMF), of a phone and converts it into binary. With the external biasing components, this binary is outputted into terminals. Relays via transistors are connected to its output terminals and turn on and off the electrical

loads depending on the number that is pressed on the resident phone.

The lights are connected to the normally open of the relay and when the relay turns on, the light turn's on too. The output signal latch therefore, even when the phone is off or the call is ended, the light still remains on(or off).

RESULTS

The operation of turning on and off the electrical loads from a remote location using the mobile phone is described thus: We have bulbs A, B and C arranged from the left-hand side to the right-hand side acting as loads. The phone connected to the circuit,

which has auto-answer feature on is called from the remote location using another mobile phone which has keypads 0 to 8.. Immediately the auto-answer feature enables the former to pick up the call, the other which initiated the call from a remote location now starts the operation of turning on and off the loads using its keypads. The result of the operation is shown in table 4.1:

TABLE 4.1 Data showing the operation of 3 loads when a certain keypad is pressed.

Keypad pressed	Load A	Load B	Load C
0	OFF OFF	OFF	OFF
1	OFF	OFF	ON
2	OFF	ON	OFF
3	OFF	ON	ON
4	ON	OFF	OFF
5	ON	OFF	ON
6	ON	ON	OFF
7	ON	ON	ON
8	OFF	OFF	OFF

FIG 5 & 6: Pictorial View of the Circuit

CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this paper which is to design a GSM control for electrical appliances has been achieved. The ability to control electrical devices from any location without any time barrier shows the huge importance of this paper.

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